

Sound sources characterization for the simulation of the acoustic environment in a library

Arianna Astolfi^a, Mariasole Modica^a, Ioana Grozeva^a, Davide Cetani^a,
Lorenzo Lavagna^a, Louena Shtrepi^a, Massimiliano Zampini^b

^a*Politecnico di Torino, Department of Energy, Corso Duca degli Abruzzi,
24, Torino, 10129, Italy*

^b*Centro Interdipartimentale Mente/Cervello - CIMEC, Corso Bettini, 31, Rovereto,
TN, 38068, Italy*

Abstract

Sound sources, typical of a library, have been characterised for the simulation of the acoustic environment with GA algorithm. In particular, Odeon 18 software has been considered. Noise from traffic, HVAC, pen clicking, turning of pages and mobile phones as well as from unintelligible and intelligible speech has been registered in anechoic conditions or in situ and was assigned with an appropriate sound power level and typology in the acoustic model. The wav samples of each source have been collected and made available for future applications in similar barely occupied environments where people intentionally tend to be quiet and require concentration. These samples can be used for auralisation of noise mixes in which the different sources contribute to different time slots according to the desired acoustic experience.

Keywords: noise source, library, acoustic simulation, realistic acoustic environment, silence, concentration, whispering, sonorisation

1. Introduction

It is often needed to simulate the acoustic environments in under construction building in order to understand their suitability for use. This is usually carried out for performance spaces, such as concert halls and theaters, by using software based on geometrical acoustics (GA) algorithms, for which a careful calibration is needed to match real and simulated sound field [1]. Virtual reconstruction of audio-video environments, such as cafeterias, domestic rooms, outdoor environments, etc. are implemented to investigate

speech intelligibility of hearing impaired subjects [2]. No study has simulated the acoustic environment of a library so far, to the authors' knowledge. This could be similar to the acoustic environment in buildings where people usually go to concentrate, slightly interact, whisper, pray, in a place where people intentionally tend to be quiet. This could be the case, apart from libraries, of churches, study rooms and museums where silence should be maintained.

To simulate the acoustic environment of a library, it is necessary to define and implement a series of sound sources representative of its typical function and occupational profile. The aim is to create a sound environment that is as realistic and consistent as possible with reference scenarios, which are other similar libraries with the same function, in order to assess the acoustic impact on users through auralisation.

The sound sources should include HVAC noise, traffic, intelligible and unintelligible speech, sounds generated by common activities such as writing, turning pages or using electronic devices, footsteps, etc. Each source should be characterised through measurements or recordings in controlled environments, such as anechoic chamber or in situ, and subsequently implemented in a 3D acoustic model used for the simulation.

In this paper the sound sources typically present in a library have been determined, their typology in the software (punctual, linear or surface) have been set, their sound power level and spectrum have been assigned, and the anechoic samples used for auralisations have been defined together with the relative recording methods.

2. Methodology

To prepare the auralisation, an anechoic signal should be associated to each source, its typology should be assigned in the simulation software (punctual, linear or surface), together with the octave-band sound power level, SWL (dB) and the directivity index, DI (dB). In the acoustic model, the SWL spectra should be flattened in frequency while preserving its overall energy, ensuring realistic frequency answer of the auralised sample. To the scope, the following formula allows to obtain the average sound power level, ASWL (dB), for each octave band to be assigned to each source:

$$ASWL = 10 \log \left(\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N 10^{\frac{SWL_i}{10}} \right) \quad (1)$$

where N is the number of octave bands and SWL_i is the sound power level for each band, in decibel. It is important to verify that the overall A-weighted SPL of the source simulated with the original non-flat spectrum should not differ so much from those obtained using the flat spectrum.

The overall SWL can be increased or decreased applying an appropriate gain, after preliminary listening tests are carried out to achieve a realistic acoustic experience with balanced sound pressure levels among sources. The following guidelines shall be applied to simulations performed in Odeon 18 software, Combined edition [3].

2.1. Anechoic samples

The origin of the anechoic samples of the noise sources typical of a library are described below, while the WAV samples can be found at [4].

2.1.1. HVAC

The Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning noise comes from heating vents or nozzles. It was recorded 10 cm far from an air conditioning nozzle in a very absorptive room.

2.1.2. Traffic

Traffic noise was recorded on the roof of a parallelepiped library, about 100 m wide, 180 m long and 18 m high, at three different distances from a busy road, that is around 90 m, 130 m and 165 m, respectively, taken at the floor level, each one corresponding to a different area of the roof, with a calibrated sound level meter (NTI, Schaan, Liechtenstein), positioned at a height of 1.5 meters from the roof floor. On the other side of the library there is a park and a less busy road.

2.1.3. Unintelligible buzz

Unintelligible buzz is a generic buzz made up of overlapping conversations, making it unintelligible. It was recorded in the anechoic chamber of Politecnico di Torino and it is composed of 6 different voices reading different texts. The voices were edited and superimposed later so that the various speeches were indistinguishable in the whole.

2.1.4. Intelligible buzz and pages, pens and mobile phone

The sound of intelligible buzzing and the noise of turning pages, pens clicking and mobile phones was recorded in the anechoic chamber of Politec-

nico di Torino, with a calibrated sound level meter (NTI, Schaan, Liechtenstein). A set simulating a library environment was constructed, consisting of a table on which a mobile phone, which emitted the sound of alerts, a calculator, pens and a notebook were placed to create realistic sound stimuli. Two microphones were used, positioned at different heights and angles in relation to the sound source in order to capture the sound towards the different receivers expected in the simulation, at a constant distance of 1.5 meters. No significant differences were detected in the different directions, thus the sources have been considered omnidirectional.

2.1.5. Equivalent sentences

Files containing 5-words sentences which are syntactically correct but semantically meaningless are used to simulate speech without affecting acoustic perception [5]. Each sentence was set to the same root-mean-square level. Equivalent sentences are based on six lists of 20 sentences of 5-words, which are equivalent with respect to the speech intelligibility outcome in noise in the Italian language. The Italian sentences are compatible with an increasing number of sentences that implement the same format in other languages [6].

The sentences can be used to ensure that each auralised sound track is different from the other, but with an equivalent acoustic content. This approach makes it possible to generate several variants of the final auralised sound while keeping the acoustic content equivalent in terms of sound pressure level, spectral distribution and speech duration.

2.1.6. Footsteps

To create the anechoic sound of the steps, samples from the Edward Foley Art [7] library for the Virtual Studio Tool (VST) NI Kontakt [8] were used. This library provides a range of customisable sound samples, allowing the user to adjust parameters such as footwear type and walking surface. In this case, women's shoes with heels were chosen. The surface material was ceramic, the same as the library floor. A total of 49 distinct footstep samples were produced, each exhibiting subtle variations in tone and dynamics while maintaining overall similarity. These samples were individually assigned to different omnidirectional point source arrays. The impulse response (IR) for each source was calculated and convolved with its respective footstep sample to obtain the auralisation of each individual step. Subsequently, the resulting individual auralizations were imported into the Digital Audio Workstation (DAW) Pro Tools [9] where they were arranged in a sequence

with an inter-step interval of approximately and 0.25 seconds, for faster footsteps, and 0.5 seconds, for slower footsteps. The final result was two separate tracks: one for fast footsteps, which simulates a person going fast down the stairs, and one for slow footsteps, that simulates people walking.

2.2. Sound sources characterization

The overall levels for each source are reported in Table 1 and Figure 1 shows the sound power levels spectra in octave band. All the sources have been considered omnidirectional.

2.2.1. HVAC

The HVAC noise can be applied to linear or surface sources. The overall A-weighted SWL of the source of 44 dB has been set. However, this SWL should be adjusted with an appropriate gain to comply with the overall A-weighted SPL at the hearing level in the main hall in positions close to the HVAC source, as reported in the Italian standard UNI-11532-2 [10].

2.2.2. Traffic

Octave band traffic noise levels, recorded on the roof of a library at three different distances from the street, were used to derive the corresponding sound pressure levels inside the library taking into account the sound insulation properties of the roofing layers, which is $R_w = 30$ dB [11]. The following formula was then used to derive the sound power level, SWL (dB), in octave bands, which takes into account the sound absorption of the room [12]:

$$SWL = SPL_{int} + 10 \log(A_{tot}) - 6 \quad (2)$$

Where SPL_{int} (dB) is the internal sound pressure level, A_{tot} (m^2) is the total area of sound-absorbing surface in the room.

2.2.3. Unintelligible buzz

Unintelligible buzz was applied to the area of the tables, as surface source at the mouth height (1.2 m). In these positions it is expected that individuals might be seated and engaged in activities such as reading, studying and conversing with a relative low voice volume.

2.2.4. *Intelligible buzz and pages, pens and mobile phone*

The sound power level of these sources has been assigned to omnidirectional point sources randomly distributed in the library. Since the recordings of the sound pressure level were made in free field 1.5 m far from the source, the following formula was used to derive the SWL (dB) for each octave band:

$$SWL = SPL + 11 + 20 \log_{10}(1.5) \quad (3)$$

where SPL (dB) is the octave band sound pressure level measured in an anechoic chamber.

2.2.5. *Equivalent sentences*

This source should be assigned to the closest omnidirectional point source to each receiver in the Odeon 18 model in order to simulate a person chatting close. Equation 3 should be applied substituting 1.5 m with 1 m to obtain the SWL from the SPL measured in free field at a distance of 1 m from the speaker's mouth, approximated as an omnidirectional point source with an overall A-weighted SPL of 47 dB, i.e., a whispered speech.

2.2.6. *Footsteps*

The sound of footsteps in Odeon 18 can be achieved by placing different sound sources along the intended path, with a linear arrangement for the steps and a distribution at different heights to simulate the descending of the stairs. The sound of footsteps is created as array of omnidirectional point sources. An array of 35 point sources simulated a person descending the stairs quickly, while an arrays of 14 omnidirectional point sources simulated a person walking slowly inside the library.

Table 1: Sound source types and corresponding overall sound power levels defined for the 3D GA simulation of a library in Odeon 18.

Source name	Source type	Overall power level (dB)
HVAC	Surface, Line	50.7
Traffic at around 90 m, 130 m, and 165 m from a busy road, on the roof of a library about 100 m wide, 180 m long, 18 m high	Surface	69.3, 56.6, 55.4
Unintelligible buzz	Surface	69.8
Intelligible buzz	Point	60.2
Equivalent sentences	Point	60.2
Pages, pens, etc.	Point	51.2
Footsteps (people descending stairs quickly)	Point (35 in a row)	54.7
Footsteps (people walking)	Point (14 for two rows)	53.3

Figure 1: Sound Power Level in octave bands for each source.

3. Conclusion

In this work a methodology for sonorisation of under construction environments within GA software has been proposed. The starting point is the choice of the sound sources typically recognisable in the environment made by comparison with similar existing settings. The second phase is the acquisition of the anechoic wav samples of these sources and their characterisation in terms of typology, sound power level and directivity. The previous phases allow the auralisation of the single sounds and the creation of noise mixes in which the different sources contribute to different time slots according to the desired acoustic experience. The case study focused on a library environment where various sources, such as HVAC, traffic, pen clicking, page turning, mobile phones and both intelligible and unintelligible speech, were recorded either in situ or under anechoic conditions. Each of these sound sources was then categorized and assigned a corresponding sound power level and classification within the acoustic model. Wav files for each individual noise source were gathered and archived for potential future use in comparable low-occupancy settings where users are expected to maintain silence and high levels of concentration.

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